

5. The world of Galaxies

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Galaxies: General and morphological classification

A Galaxy is a gravitationally bound, large collection of Stars, planetary systems, gas nebulae and other stellar objects.

This deep-field image from the Hubble telescope shows about 1'500 different Galaxies in a section of sky just 144 arc-seconds across, illustrating the size and vastness of the universe.

Galaxies vary greatly in appearance, size and composition. Our Milky Way Galaxy is one of the larger Galaxies and has about 250 billion ($2.5 \cdot 10^{11}$) Stars with a diameter of about 170'000 light years. In addition to Stars, a Galaxy also consists of gas, cosmic dust and presumably dark matter.

The Andromeda Galaxy is our nearest larger neighbour Galaxy. The distance between these two Galaxies is 2.4 to 2.7 million light years (1 light year = $1.46 \cdot 10^{12}$ km).

Galaxies often appear in groups or clusters. Based on the "Ultra_Deep-Field images" taken by the Hubble telescope in 2004, more than 100 billion (10^{11}) could theoretically be observed. New results based on mathematical estimates give a total number of Galaxies in the observable cosmos of more than one trillion ($> 10^{12}$).

For a detailed discussion and description of the Galaxies, see Ref. R.5.1.a)

The following is an explanation of the morphological classification of Galaxies proposed by Edwin Hubble in 1928 and in the following years with the help of his large reflecting telescope.

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1. Spiral Galaxies

A **spiral Galaxy** is a disc-shaped Galaxy whose appearance shows a spiral pattern. The central region, also called the bulge, is a spherical bulge and consists mainly of older Stars.

Spiral Galaxies contain a relatively large amount of gas in the disk. This means that new Stars can be formed permanently. The spiral arms appear bluish due to the newly formed Stars here. The Galaxy is embedded in a Halo of invisible dark matter. The Halo of a Galaxy is an approximately spherical area that is larger than the Galaxy itself and in whose center the Galaxy is embedded].

Together with the so-called lenticular Galaxies, spiral Galaxies are also summarized as disk Galaxies. [In lenticular Galaxies, the Stars have arranged themselves in a disc; in contrast to spiral Galaxies, however, there are no spiral arms in lenticular Galaxies].

Spiral Galaxy Messier 101

In the case of a spiral Galaxy, the following structures can be recognised:

- A flat rotating disc of Stars, gas and dust. The disk can be divided into a thin component which contains a lot of gas and newly formed stars, and a thick disk containing mostly older Stars.
- The central area "bulge" (see above).
- It is now assumed for certain that there is a supermassive "Black hole" at the center of every Galaxy.
- The galactic Halo consists of widely scattered, older Stars and a multitude of globular clusters, which slowly orbit the Galaxy. .

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2. Barred spiral Galaxies

A barred spiral Galaxy, (Balkenspirale Galaxie) or barred Galaxy for short, is a spiral Galaxy with a more or less straight band of bright Stars. This bar extends from the center of the Galaxy to different distances, in some cases almost to the edge. The spiral arms emanate from the ends of the bar.

Barred spiral Galaxies are relatively common. Studies show that up to two-thirds of all spiral Galaxies have a barred structure. The Milky Way is also a barred spiral Galaxy.

The barred area is an active Star-forming region. Gas, from which the Stars are form, flows from the spiral arms towards the center of the Galaxy.

Barred Spiral Galaxy NGC 1055
Image taken with
"Very Large Telescope"

The bar structure is the result of a density wave that spreads radially from the center of the Galaxy and influences the orbit of the inner Stars.

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3. Elliptical Galaxies

Elliptical Galaxies are clearly different from spiral Galaxies. They do not have a spiral shape but the shape of an ellipsoid or a sphere and are otherwise structureless. Elliptical (ellipsoidal) Galaxies occur in giant and dwarf formats. Giant elliptical Galaxies are true giants in the cosmos and can contain up to a trillion (!) stars and be surrounded by several thousand spherical globular clusters !

Elliptical Galaxies consist mainly of old Stars, which is noticeable by the fact that they have a reddish colour. Small, low-mass ellipsoids can also contain younger stars (younger than 5 billion years).

The giant elliptical Galaxy NGC 1316, shown in the image on the right, is a lenticular Galaxy with an active galactic nucleus, estimated to be 73 million light years away from the Milky Way. Its diameter is huge, 225'000 light years.

Elliptische Galaxie

Elliptical Galaxy

Spiralgalaxie

Spiral Galaxy

The NGC 1316 Galaxy: a lenticular Galaxy,
i.e. an intermediate type between a
spiral and an elliptical Galaxy

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4. Irregular Galaxies

Irregular Galaxies have neither clear structures nor symmetries:

- No special symmetry plane
- Correspondingly, spiral arms are lacking
- They also do not have an elliptical shape like ellipsoidal Galaxies
- They also lack a galactic nucleus

Irregular Galaxies instead, have several irregularly distributed smaller condensations. Therefore, they cannot be classified in the Hubble sequence, but form a special class, abbreviated as "Ir" or "Irr" (Irregular). The best-known representatives of this type are the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds.

Irregular Galaxies have much less mass (between 700 and 1'300 billion solar masses) and significantly lower gravitational fields than regular galaxies: they are also on average less luminous. Irregular galaxies make up about 4% of all Galaxies.

Irregular Galaxies contain a lot of gas and dust and younger Stars that are very irregularly distributed. [Most of the older Stars are often distributed in a more regular, oblate structure and are rotating as in spiral Galaxies]. The formation of irregular Galaxies is explained in Ref. R-5-5.

Large Magellanic Cloud

The irregular dwarf Galaxy NGC 1569

5-55

Milky Way Galaxy - 1)

Diameter :

approx. $1.8 \cdot 10^5$ to $2.0 \cdot 10^5$ Lj
(approx. $17 \cdot 10^{17}$ to
 $19 \cdot 10^{17}$ km)
(1 Lj = $9.46 \cdot 10^{12}$ km)

Thickness :

ca. 10^3 Lj without Buldge
($9.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ km);
approx. 15'000 LJ with Buldge
(*)
($1.42 \cdot 10^{17}$ km)

Age :

approx. 13.6 billion years
($13.6 \cdot 10^9$ years)

Number of Stars :

100 to 400 billion
($100 \cdot 10^9$ to $400 \cdot 10^9$ Stars)
(estimated)

(*) Buldge = bulge)

Since 2016, research has assumed that there are about one trillion = 10^{12} galaxies in the observable Universe! The oldest known star in our Milky Way is about 13.2 billion years old ($13.2 \cdot 10^9$ years).

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The layered Milky Way - Galaxy - 2)

Edwin Hubble studied Galaxies and classified their types: elliptical, lenticular and spiral. The spiral Galaxies are dischshaped with spiral arms (see Figure from p. 56 of the Milky Way system).

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On our Milky Way Galaxy: Facts and Explanations

The Milky Way, or simply Galaxy, is the Galaxy that is home to our solar system. It is a barred spiral Galaxy of the so-called "Local Group of Galaxies", to which the Andromeda Galaxy also belongs. Our Galaxy is one of a trillion ($\approx 10^{12}$) Galaxies in the observed universe, according to findings of 2016.

The stellar disk of the Milky Way (see pp 56 and 57) has a diameter of about 180'000 to 200,000 light years (Lj) ($9.5 \cdot 10^{17}$ km) and the mean thickness is estimated to be about 1000 Lj ($9.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ km). It is estimated that it consists of 100 to 400 billion Stars; the exact number depends on the very light Stars, the number of which is very uncertain.

The relative size of the Milky Way can be illustrated as follows: if it were reduced to 10 m, the width of our solar system (including the Oort, a spherical cloud of comets), would be only about 0.1 mm! This corresponds to a factor of 100'000 (!).

Using the estimated age of the global cluster (about 13.4 billion years = $13.4 \cdot 10^9$ years), the age of the oldest Stars in the Milky Way is about 13.6 billion years. Based on the latest scientific findings, our Galaxy is estimated to be about 14 billion years old.

The galactic disk, which is inflated in its center, has a diameter of between 180'000 and 200'000 Lj. The distance from our Sun to the galactic center is now estimated at $26'000 \pm 1'400$ Lj. The center of the Milky Way lies in the constellation Sagittarius and is hidden behind dark gas clouds so that it cannot be observed directly in visible light.

The galactic center contains a compact object with a very large mass, which can be inferred from the motion of material around this center. The intense radio source Sagittarius A*, which is considered to be the center of mass of the Milky Way system, has recently been identified as a **super heavy "black hole"**. It is assumed that most Galaxies have a "black hole" at their centers.

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Andromeda Galaxy - 1)

The Andromeda Galaxy is the closest spiral Galaxy to the Milky Way. It contains billions of stars. The distance between our Galaxy and the Andromeda Galaxy is unimaginably large, about 2.4 to 2.7 million light years (approx. 25 trillion km = $25 \cdot 10^{18}$ km). The Andromeda Galaxy is the most distant object that can be observed with the naked eye under good conditions without technical aids. The Andromeda Galaxy is often referred to as M 31, after the entry in the Messier catalogue. The Messier catalogue was first published by the French astronomer Charles Messier in 1771; it consists of a list of 110 astronomical objects, mainly Galaxies, Star clusters and nebulae].

← Andromedy - Galaxy

Some important data:

- Distance from Earth: 2.56 million light years
- Brightness (visual): 3.5 mag ((magnitude)
- Mass: between 0.7 and $2.5 \cdot 10^{12}$ solar masses
- Diameter: 200'000 Lj ; 1 Lj = $9.461 \cdot 10^{12}$ km

For the motion of the Andromeda Galaxy in relation to the Milky Way, the radial velocity in the direction of the center of the Milky Way is 114 km/s (approx. 410'000 km/h) and a transverse velocity of 60 km/s has been determined. With the help of measurements from the Esa satellite Gaja, the project researchers were able to record the motions of both Galaxies more precisely than ever before. From this, they calculated that the collision of the Andromeda Galaxy with the Milky Way Galaxy will occur in 4.5 billion years (= $4.5 \cdot 10^9$ years), so no need to worry ! The course of the collision orbit is complex because of the transverse velocity and is described in more detail in Ref. R-5-9, p. 59 b).

5-59

Andromeda Galaxy 2)

The Hubble Space Telescope has shown that the Andromeda Galaxy hosts a massive **Black Hole** of 140 million solar masses.

The new data rule out astrophysical alternatives to a **Black Hole**. The **Black Hole** is surrounded by a small disk of young Stars whose origin is unclear.

More detailed data about **Black Holes** in Galaxies are compiled on pages 62 and 63.

The center of the
Andromeda Galaxy M 31 :

The image shows the Hubble Space Telescope image of the center of M 31 and the model (bottom right, enlarged compared to the image) of the nucleus, a disk of blue stars closely orbiting the **Black Hole** and elliptically orbiting Red Stars.

5-60

Giant Galaxy NGC 1316

The Galaxy NGC 1316 is a Galaxy that has already been listed on p. 5-54 as an example of a lenticular Galaxy. A lenticular Galaxy is an intermediate type between spiral and elliptical Galaxies. NGC 1316 is a giant Galaxy also known as Fornax A and APR 154.

With an apparent magnitude of 8.4 mag (mag = magnitude), NGV 1316 is the brightest member of the Fornax Galaxy cluster, which is about 70 million light years (Lj) away, and is one of the brightest Galaxies which is not in the "Local Group" or one of the immediately neighbouring Galaxy groups. Its angular extent is 11.0' x 7.2' (1' = 1 arcsecond), from which a diameter of about 255'000 Lj can be deduced. This makes it twice as large as our Milky Way Galaxy. As one of the brightest radio sources in the sky, it is also called Fornax A in the usual way for large radio Galaxies (A radio Galaxy is an active Galaxy whose exceptionally strong continuum synchrotron radiation can be observed in the radio wave range).

NGC 1316 (Fornax A) - Galaxy

Images from the Hubble Space Telescope reveal details that help us reconstruct the history of this giant jumble. Detailed wide-angle images show huge collisional envelopes, while accurate images of the center show that there are only a few globular clusters inside NGC 1316. Such effects are to be expected in Galaxies that have had collisions or mergers with other Galaxies in the last billion years. The dark knots and dust lanes in the image suggest that one or more of the intertwined Galaxies were originally spiral Galaxies.

NGC 1316 is about 50'000 Lj across and lies about 60 million Lj away in the constellation Chemical Furnace (Fornax).

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Black Hole: Definition and Description

A **Black Hole** is an object whose mass is concentrated in an extremely small volume and, as a result of this compactness, generates such strong gravity in its immediate vicinity that not even light can pass through and leave this area. The outer edge of this region is called the **event horizon** because everything that happens inside this "shell" remains unobservable to the outside world. Thus, **Black Holes** are apparently no longer part of our Universe.

Nothing can cross an event horizon from the inside to the outside - no information, no radiation and certainly no matter. The fact that a "way out" is no longer even conceivable is conclusively described by General Relativity through an extreme curvature of space-time.

Vivid illustration of a **Black Hole**

To the adjacent illustration of a **Black Hole**

Ray A: is only slightly deflected from its path

Ray B is already more strongly influenced and more clearly deflected

Ray C changes its direction of motion so strongly that it is suddenly deflected.

Ray D is forced into an orbit around the **Black Hole**.

Ray E comes so close to the **Black Hole's** sphere of influence that there is no escape for it, its photons cross the Event Horizon and fall into the hole.

Or to put it another way: the gravity of a **Black Hole** is so great that the escape velocity (the speed a body needs to leave a larger one) is not only 7.8 km/s, as on Earth, but should be greater than the speed of light !

5-62

Black Hole in the Galaxy Messier 87 discovered

At the center of many, perhaps even all Galaxies, there is a **Black Hole**. It is an extreme place where so much mass is concentrated in a very small space that even light can no longer escape the force of gravity. Although postulated by some scientists for some time, e.g. by **Karl Schwarzschild** and **Stephen Hawking**, no such gravity monster had ever been observed until recently.

But the image of the so-called "Event Horizon Telescope" presented below is real. It has become possible because, after years of preparatory work, researchers have interconnected numerous radio telescopes worldwide in such a way that they function as a single gigantic observation center. This has created a virtual telescope whose image sharpness corresponds to that of a single antenna with a diameter of 8'000 km. This makes it possible to image the comparatively small area of a **Black Hole** in sufficient detail. The eight facilities used include the "Alma" telescope in Chile with 66 giant radio dishes, the telescope of the European Southern Observatory, also in Chile, the IRAM 30-metre telescope Pico Veleta in the Spanish Sierra Nevada, as well as a telescope at the South Pole.

The researchers made their observations inside the very active Galaxy Messier 87, or M87 for short, which lies in the region of the constellation Virgo. This **Black Hole** is 55 million light years away from Earth. It has a mass of about 6.6 billion solar masses.

Black Hole in the Galaxy Messier 87 (2017)

There is also a **Black Hole** inside our Galaxy, the Milky Way. Astronomers call it Sagittarius A*. It is only about 26'000 light years away from Earth and has a mass of about 4.1 million solar masses. An attempt was also made to take a picture of Sagittarius A*. However, this was not successful at first, partly because the heart of the Milky Way is hidden by a dense nebula of charged particles, which makes observation difficult.

5-63

Appendix: Chapter 5

A-5-0

Edin Hubble (1889 – 1953)

Edwin Hubble

Edwin Hubble was an American astronomer. He classified the spiral Galaxies, dealt with the expansion of the Universe and discovered the Hubble constant H , as well as the red shift of starlight with increasing distance ("Hubble effect"). He is the namesake of the Hubble Space Telescope (see picture below).

The Mount Wilson Observatory was built in 1917 at an altitude of 1742 m in the San Mountains in the US state of California. It has a 2.5 m mirror and was the largest reflecting telescope in the world for 30 years.

Hubble's Hook mirror telescope on Mount Wilson

In April 1990, the space telescope named Hubble in honour of Hubble set out to explore space aboard the space shuttle Discovery. Since then, it has circled the Earth many thousands of times, taking aim at thousands of objects and capturing them in millions of photographs.

Hubble has looked up to 13 billion light years deep into the Universe and far into the cosmic past.

Hubble Space Telescope (1990)

Every week, the observatory sends around 120 gigabytes of data to Earth. Its main task is to study specific points in space for various research projects.

Hubble is also the founder of the Big Bang theory.

A-5-1

A-5-0 / A-5-1

Collision of two Galaxies

The Hubble Space Telescope has photographed an unusual Galaxy collision. The two merging Galaxies look like a cosmic face. Apparently, two Galaxies have collided head-on at a distance of around 704 million light years from our cosmic home, the Milky Way.

The central region of the two colliding Galaxies form the two "eyes" of the formation, as the European "Hubble" Information Center in Garching near Munich announced shortly before Halloween (31 January 2010).

"Hubble telescope observes collision of two Galaxies

A-5-2

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R-5-0

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R-5-2 / R-5-3